

THE IMPACT OF INFLATION ON STOCK RETURNS: EVIDENCE FROM FOUR EMERGING MARKETS USING PANEL CO-INTEGRATION TEST

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ABSTRACT

The existing literature on the impact of inflation on stock market has shown diverse results. This paper tries to establish long term relationship between stock prices and consumer price index by using monthly time series and panel data on both the variables for emerging economies including Brazil, Russia, India and China. Various statistical tests including traditional Johansen cointegration test and Pedroni (Engle-Granger based) panel cointegration tests have been employed to establish long run equilibrium relationship between stock prices and inflation. Unit root tests including Augmented Dickey Fuller test and Phillips-Perron test have been used to check the stationarity of data. The findings of this study show absence of any association between stock prices and inflation in short as well as long run for the BRIC countries. Thus, the study reveals that, inflation is not a critical factor affecting stock returns for the BRIC countries.

Keywords: Stock Index, Consumer Price Index, BRIC, Unit root test, Johansen Cointegration test, Pedroni Panel Cointegration test.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most debatable issues in finance literature has been the functioning of the stock market and its impact on the overall economic development. Stock market is considered as the engine of growth for any economy. It is one the vital component of an economic system as it enhances growth of all its sectors. It provides a mechanism for the efficient utilization of scarce resources by channelizing savings from surplus sectors towards deficit sectors. Stock returns determine how efficiently scarce resources are being utilized and provide a measure of performance of stock markets. A number of firm specific and macro economic variables have been identified to impact stock market performance. Inflation, among other macroeconomic variables, is considered to be one of the most important and crucial factors impacting stock returns. Inflation is the rise in general level of prices of goods and services over a period of time. One of the earliest

attempts establishing relationship between stock returns and inflation spurts out of Irving Fisher's theory of interest rates (1930). As per the hypothesis proposed by Fisher, real asset returns should positively move with expected inflation rate and as such stock market provides hedge against inflation. This implies that investors are fully compensated for increases in the general price level through corresponding increases in the nominal stock market returns and thus the real returns remain unaffected. In contrast several studies emerged (eg. Lintner (1975), Fama (1982), Geske and Roll (1983)) which consistently rejected the Fisherian hypothesis. Later, two important approaches, tax effect hypothesis by Feldstein (1980) and proxy hypothesis by Fama (1981) emerged to provide explanations regarding the positive relationship between stock returns and inflation. Feldstein (1980) observed that inflation generates artificial capital gains which are subject to taxation and thus, in an

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inflationary situation corporate face increased tax liabilities. The ultimate effect is a reduction in the real after tax earnings. This will lead to reduction in common stock valuations by rational investors causing movement in share prices. Fama (1981) proposed the proxy hypothesis, according to which, an increase in inflation rates reduce demand for money and thus reduce real economic activity. This, in turn, leads to reduction in future corporate profits and thus decline in stock prices.

The present paper attempts to establish the long term relationship between stock returns and inflation for four of the major emerging countries including Brazil, Russia, India and China also referred to as BRIC nations. The four BRIC countries represent a combined nominal GDP of US\$ 16.428 trillion i.e., about 20% of world GDP.

The rest of the paper is arranged in the following fashion: section 2 reviews the existing literature related to the study, Section 3 presents the data and methodology, section 4 discusses the empirical analysis and its interpretation and finally section 5 presents the conclusion and implications of the study.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The relationship between stock returns and inflation has been extensively researched for developed, emerging and developing countries over the past few decades. Some of them have revealed the presence of negative relationship between stock returns and inflation. On the other hand, some of the studies have documented a positive relationship between stock returns and inflation. Thus, the evidence regarding the stock returns-inflation

relationship is still debatable. Following are the prominent ones:

Fama (1981), among the earliest studies on the relationship between stock returns and inflation, revealed an indirect negative relationship between the stock returns and inflation. Fama, in this study, hypothesized the proxy effect stating that the negative inflation-stock returns relationship is induced by the negative relations between inflation and real activity.

Boudoukh and Richardson (1993) studied the relationship between stock returns & inflation for U.S. & U.K. markets, using OLS and variance-covariance matrix. The study revealed a negative short-run and positive long-run relationship between inflation & stock returns.

Chatrath, Ramchander and Song (1996) used ARMA model to study the relationship between stock returns and inflation for India and revealed a negative relationship consistent with the proxy hypothesis.

Floros (2004) documented a significant positive short-run relationship between stock returns and lagged values of inflation for Greece. However the study did not support any evidence for the presence of any significant long-run relationship between the variables.

Shanmugam and Misra (2008) explained the negative relationship between inflationary trend and real returns to emerge from the unexpected portion of inflation for India.

Geetha, Rosle, Chandran and Chong (2011) analyzed the effect of inflation on stock market returns for Malaysia, U.S.A. & China. The co-integration test revealed existence of negative

long-run relationship for all the three countries and vector error correction model determined short-run relationship for Malaysia & U.S.

Naser and Shah (2012), while studying the stock returns-inflation relationship for India, found a negative and statistically significant relationship between the two variables.

Kalu and Solomon (2013) investigated whether stock returns protect investors against inflation in Nigeria. The two-step Engle-Granger method revealed the presence of long-run integrating equilibrium between the stock returns and inflation adjusting at a very slow rate.

Samiran (2013) also studied the inflation-stock returns relationship for India and revealed that, the pre-reform period supported the Fisherian hypothesis, while as in the post-reform period the study is in agreement with the Fama's hypothesis, in contrast to Shanmugam and Misra (2008).

Azar (2014) studied the relationship between stock returns and inflation for U.S.A. using OLS and e-GARCH model. The study signified the presence of significant negative relationship between stock returns and inflation.

Tripathi and Kumar (2015) reported presence of long term equilibrium relationship for China

and Brazil while studying BRICS nations.

Thus, a number of studies have confirmed the presence of both positive and negative stock return-inflation relationship. However, very few studies have been done particularly for the BRIC economies. This study attempts to cover the research gap by investigating the long run dynamics between stock returns and inflation for Brazil, Russia, India and China.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data

The present study utilizes monthly time series data on stock price index and consumer price index of BRIC countries for a period from January 2001 to October 2015 covering 179 monthly observations. Change in consumer price index month on month has been taken as proxy for inflation rate for all the four countries. The data on inflation was collected from OECD database. For stock returns, change in monthly closing stock index values of prominent benchmark indices of the respective countries has been taken from Yahoo finance. The following table shows the stock exchange and respective benchmark index for the BRIC countries.

Country	Stock Exchange	Stock Index
Brazil	Sao Paulo Stock Exchange	IBOVESPA
Russia	Moscow Stock Exchange	RTSI INDEX
India	Bombay Stock Exchange	S&P BSE SENSEX
China	Shanghai Stock Exchange	SSE Composite Index

3.2. METHODOLOGY

3.2.1. Descriptive Statistics

Mean, Median, Maximum, Minimum, Std. Dev., Skewness, Kurtosis have been used to identify and summarize the general trends of the data set.

3.2.2. Bi-variate Correlation

For each of the sample country bi-variate correlation has been computed between stock returns and inflation rates to establish the direction and magnitude of short term relationship between the two variables.

3.2.3. Unit Root Tests

The first step of any statistical analysis is to check the stationary properties of time series data being employed in order to draw meaningful inferences. In order to check stationarity properties of time series, we have used Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test and Phillips-Perron (PP) test. The unit root tests used in the study have null hypothesis of presence of unit root properties in data, or simply non-stationarity of data. The stationarity of data in both tests have been checked at both log levels as well as at their 1st differences.

3.2.4. Johansen Cointegration Test

If a variable has unit-root property, it is non-stationary as the case with time series data, and thus Cointegration relationship is examined. When variables are non-stationary, estimation by using linear regression yields misleading and incorrect result. Johansen Cointegration test has been used to test the long term relationship between stock prices and consumer price index. The test has been applied individually to all the sample countries in order to establish whether there is presence

of long-run association between stock prices and consumer prices. The Johansen Cointegration test is based on error correction representation of the p order Vector Autoregressive model with Gaussian error:

$$X_t = \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \Gamma_i X_{t-i} + \epsilon_t$$

The two likelihood ratio tests were developed by Johansen for testing no of Cointegration vectors.

The Trace test given by:

$$\text{trace}(r) = -T \sum_{i=r+1}^g \ln(1 - \lambda_i)$$

And, the Maximum eigenvalue test given by:

$$\lambda_{\max}(r, r+1) = T \ln(1 - \lambda_{r+1})$$

The null hypothesis of the trace statistics test is that there is no Cointegration. The alternative hypothesis is that there are more than 0 Cointegration vectors. The null hypothesis of the eigenvalue statistics is r cointegrating vectors against the alternative of $r+1$ cointegrating vectors.

3.2.5. Pedroni (Engle-Granger based) Cointegration Tests

To determine whether any long term equilibrium relation exists between stock prices and consumer price index for BRIC countries when panel data is used, Pedroni (Engle-Granger based) Cointegration tests have been used. When two series are cointegrated it means that even though both data series are non-stationary, there is some long-run equilibrium relationship linking both series so that relationship is stationary.

The Pedroni Cointegration tests are Engel-

Granger (1987) residual based panel cointegration tests with more than one independent variable in the regression equation. Considering the following regression equation:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 t + \gamma_{1i} X_{1i,t} + \gamma_{2i} X_{2i,t} + \dots + \gamma_{Mi} X_{Mi,t} + e_{i,t}$$

For t (number of observations over time) = 1 to T, i (number of individual members in the panel) = 1 to N, and m (number of independent variables) = 1 to M; and x and y are integrated of order 1, i.e., I(1). Here α_i and β_1 are individual and trend effects, which if desired can be set to zero.

The Pedroni cointegration test provides null hypothesis of no cointegration, where the residuals, $e_{i,t}$, are integrated of order one or simply I(1). The following auxiliary regression equation is used to test the residuals obtained in the above equation whether they are integrated of order one or not.

$$e_{i,t} = \alpha_i e_{i,t-1} + u_{i,t}$$

Various methods have been described by Pedroni for constructing statistics for testing

null hypothesis of no cointegration ($\rho_i = 1$). Broadly two alternative hypothesis have been proposed in this test; homogenous alternative referred to as within-dimension test and heterogeneous alternative referred to as between-dimension test.

4. Empirical Analysis and Economic Interpretation

Table 1 provides descriptive statistics of index returns and inflation rate for all the four BRIC countries. As from the table, India has the highest average return (0.010) followed by Russia (0.009) and Brazil (0.005). China has the lowest average return (0.003). Risk measured in terms of standard deviation has been found highest for Russia (0.101) followed by China (0.082), Brazil (0.071) and India (0.069) with the lowest standard deviation. With regards to inflation, Russia has the highest inflation followed by India and Brazil, while China has the lowest inflation.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Statistic	Brazil Index Returns	Brazil Inflation	Russia Index Returns	Russia Inflation	India Index Returns	India Inflation	China Index Returns	China Inflation
Mean	0.005	0.005	0.009	0.008	0.010	0.006	0.003	0.002
Median	0.006	0.005	0.019	0.007	0.011	0.006	0.006	0.001
Maximum	0.164	0.030	0.267	0.038	0.249	0.045	0.242	0.026
Minimum	-0.284	-0.002	-0.449	-0.004	-0.273	-0.016	-0.283	-0.013
Std. Dev.	0.071	0.004	0.101	0.006	0.069	0.007	0.082	0.006
Skewness	-0.511	2.508	-0.760	1.417	-0.527	0.537	-0.403	0.354
Kurtosis	3.920	14.662	5.069	5.952	4.877	6.641	4.133	3.565

Table 2 presents the results of bi-variate correlations between index returns and inflation for all the four BRIC countries. It is evident from the table that, Brazil, Russia and

China, all have positive low correlation coefficients. Also, the coefficients are statistically insignificant. The results also show that India alone has negative correlation

between index returns and inflation. However, the coefficient is very low and statistically insignificant. The bi-variate correlation results

thus reveal that stock returns and inflation are not having any significant association in the short run.

Table 2. Bi-variate correlations between index returns and inflation

Variables	Value	Probability
Brazil index returns and inflation	0.014	0.851
Russia index returns and inflation	0.037	0.637
India index returns and inflation	-0.057	0.451
China index returns and inflation	0.111	0.142

For Cointegration analysis, we test for the stationarity of available time series of stock index and consumer price index for all the sample countries. As a prerequisite for Cointegration, the variables should be non-stationary at level and stationary at first differenced. In other words, variables should be integrated of order one I (1). Table 3 shows

unit root test results for stock index and consumer price index (CPI), using ADF and PP unit root tests, for all the BRIC countries. Both the variables have been found to be non-stationary at level and stationary at first difference in both unit root tests for the four countries.

Table 3 Unit Root Test Results

Variable	Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test				Phillips –Perron (PP) Test			
	Log Level		1 st Differenced		Log Level		1 st Differenced	
	Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Intercept	Trend & Intercept
Brazil Index	-1.57	-1.44	-11.41*	-11.44*	-1.50	-1.46	-11.44*	-11.44*
Brazil Inflation	1.77	0.80	-1.46	-2.04	2.53	1.23	-5.24*	-5.62*
Russia Index	-2.36	-2.19	-10.69*	-10.75*	-2.05	-1.72	-10.68*	-10.74*
Russia Inflation	1.93	-0.25	-1.08	-1.87	2.64	0.04	-5.91*	-6.05*
India Index	-0.31	-3.41***	-13.07*	-13.06*	-0.43	-3.11	-13.13*	-13.11*
India Inflation	1.25	-1.91	-1.76	-2.82	3.58	-1.21	-9.52*	-10.23*
China Index	-2.84**	-3.82***	-4.83*	-4.81*	-2.22	-2.63	-12.41*	-12.38*
China Inflation	-0.56	-3.88*	-2.76***	-2.64	0.50	-3.36***	-9.97*	-9.99*

(* , ** , *** represent significance at 1%, 5% and 10% level)

In order to establish long-run relationship between stock index values and consumer price index, Unrestricted Cointegration test (Trace)

within Johansen framework has been used. The test results are presented in Table 4. As per the results, in the Indian context, trace statistic

value is greater than the critical values at 5% significance level. This implies presence of two cointegrating equations. Thus it confirms the presence of statistically significant cointegrating or long term equilibrium

relationship between stock prices and consumer price index for India. However, for all the other sample countries, the results show absence of any Cointegration or long term relationship between stock prices and CPI.

Table 4 Johansen Co-integration Test Results

Country	Hypothesized no of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Probability
Brazil	None	0.05	11.09	15.49	0.21
	At most 1	0.02	2.89	3.84	0.09
Russia	None	0.03	10.28	15.49	0.26
	At most 1*	0.02	4.35	3.84	0.03
India	None*	0.06	16.35	15.49	0.04
	At most 1*	0.03	5.73	3.84	0.02
China	None	0.08	13.84	15.49	0.09
	At most 1	0.00	0.62	3.84	0.80

Finally, Pedroni Co-integration Tests has been applied to establish long run relationship between stock index prices and consumer price index, while using panel data. Table 5 reveals absence of any equilibrium or long term relationship between stock prices and consumer price index for BRIC countries. For

majority of the tests of Pedroni panel co-integration, the null hypothesis of no co-integration has been accepted by significant margin. Hence, Pedroni panel co-integration tests results support the individual Johansen co-integration test results for each of the four countries.

Table 5 Pedroni Panel Cointegration Test Results

		Deterministic Intercept and No Deterministic Trend		Deterministic Intercept and Deterministic Trend		No Deterministic Intercept or Deterministic Trend	
		Simple	Weighted	Simple	Weighted	Simple	Weighted
Panel v-stat	statistic	1.147	2.156	3.337	2.509	2.894	3.971
	(probability)	(0.125)	(0.015)	(0.000)	(0.006)	(0.002)	(0.000)
Panel rho-stat	statistic	0.404	-0.677	-3084	-2.208	-0.986	-1.589
	(probability)	(0.657)	(0.249)	(0.001)	(0.013)	(0.162)	(0.056)
Panel PP-stat	statistic	0.881	-0.306	-2.282	-1.728	-0.800	-1.196
	(probability)	(0.811)	(0.379)	(0.011)	(0.042)	(0.212)	(0.116)
Panel ADF-stat	statistic	1.714	0.068	-2.304	-1.766	-0.298	-0.982
	(probability)	(0.956)	(0.527)	(0.010)	0.038	(0.382)	(0.163)
Group rho-stat	statistic	0.072	NA	-1.151	NA	-0.277	NA
	(probability)	(0.528)		(0.124)		(0.391)	
Group PP-stat	statistic	0.147	NA	-1.284	NA	-0.977	NA
	(probability)	(0.558)		(0.099)		(0.164)	
Group ADF-stat	statistic	0.479	NA	-1.323	NA	-0.755	NA
	(probability)	(0.684)		(0.092)		(0.225)	

5. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The paper attempts to examine the relationship between stock prices and inflation both in the short and long run. While as, simple correlation technique has been used to examine the direction and magnitude of association between stock returns and inflation in the short run, more complicated techniques including traditional Johansen cointegration test and Pedroni (Engle-Granger) panel cointegration tests have been employed to establish long term equilibrium relationship between stock prices and consumer prices. We have found that stock returns and inflation rate are not having any association in short run. Apart from

this, there is absence of any long run relationship between stock prices and consumer price index for Brazil, Russia and China. While as, Johansen cointegration test has revealed long run equilibrium relationship in the Indian context. Further, Pedroni panel cointegration tests have confirmed the results of traditional Johansen cointegration test by establishing absence of any long run relationship between stock prices and consumer price index for the BRIC countries. Thus, results of this study imply that equity does not provide any hedge against inflation in the long run for the BRIC countries. It can be concluded that, inflation is not a critical factor

impacting stock returns for the BRIC countries. Hence, other macroeconomic variables should be further analyzed in order to find out the critical factors affecting stock returns.

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